

THE VITAMIN B COMPLEX IN TOXIC CONDITIONS.

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The effects of aneurin, lactoflavin and frankonite filtrate of aqueous yeast extract in toxic conditions caused by 15% codliver oil in foods of a colony of white rats weighing 50-60 g. each, have been tried. All of them cause detoxication but lactoflavin seems to be most effective. Vitamin B complex acts better than any of the factors alone.

Agdhar (*Acta Paediatrica*, 1926, 8, 319; 1926, 6, 165; 1928, 7, 289; 1928, 8, 364; 1929, 8, 489; 1929, 9, 170) had found that large amount of codliver oil given to animals produced toxic effects, which were curable with large amounts of yeast. Norris and Church (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, 437) had also found the same thing and it appears from their work that aneurin is the factor concerned in preventing the toxic conditions. De Vries and Puister (*Ext. Archiv. Nèerl. Physiol.*, 1933, 16, 71) also worked on the same problem and they are of opinion that the vitamin B₂ is the factor in the yeast which cures the toxic conditions caused by the administration of large amounts of codliver oil. But in none of their experiments they have used the pure vitamins aneurin and B₂. Sometime back Coward and her co-workers ("The biological Standardisation of the Vitamins," London, 1938) had shown to some extent that the different factors of the vitamin B complex are to some degree replaceable by the other factors of the same vitamin (using growth effect as the criterion). Mukherji ("The Role of Aneurin-vitamin B₁ and Vitamin D in Guanidine and Methylguanidine poisoning", Amsterdam University, 1938, p. 8) had also found the same thing from another aspect. He had shown that the aneurin neutralises the toxic effects of the guanidine bodies but if the vitamin B complex was used instead of the aneurin alone then the amount of aneurin required to neutralise the effect of the same amount of guanidine was much less than before. Hariette Chick (*Lancet*, 1933, 2, 341) had found that pellagra is caused by a toxic substance derived from a corn diet which effect could be corrected by a water-soluble substance associated with the vitamin B₂. It was thought desirable at this stage to find out individually the effects of the different factors of the vitamin B complex in neutralising the toxic effects of the same substance. With this end in view the present work was undertaken with large quantities of codliver oil and the different factors of the vitamin B complex in a chemically pure state wherever they are available. It is found that the vitamins aneurin, lactoflavin and a heat-labile factor in the B₂ complex (=vit. B complex - vit. B₁ and 2) are potent detoxicating agents; the latter two factors being again more potent than aneurin in neutralising the toxic effects of large amounts of codliver oil.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

The animals used in this work were young white rats weighing about 50 g. each. They were taken from the same colony. Aneurin used was prepared by Hoffmann (La Roche, Basle) and the vitamin B₂ (lactoflavin) in the Laboratory of Physiological Chemistry, University of Amsterdam, both of them being synthetically prepared pure crystals. Aneurin (0.1 mg.) was injected and lactoflavin (0.05 mg.) daily to those animals receiving them by the intraperitoneal route, Sundays and some holidays being excepted. Other factors of the vitamin B complex were used as dried whole yeast, autoclaved yeast and frankonite filtrate from aqueous extract of yeast. Nicotinic acid was also tried. All these were administered, mixed with food. It has been found that better results were obtained if the foods were prepared fresh about twice a week, specially during the summer days. Otherwise it has been found that foods get more toxic and the results are vitiated unexpectedly. In foods Mu 1, 2, 5 and 16, 3% autoclaved yeast were used instead of whole yeast. In each case the total amount of washed rice, oil, and yeast was kept constant. Mu 1 and 7 had daily 0.1 mg. aneurin; Mu 2 and 12, 0.05 mg. lactoflavin intraperitoneally, Mu 8 had frankonite filtrate from aqueous extract of 200 g. of yeast per kg. of the food. Composition of foods is shown in Table I.

TABLE I.

Composition table of diets used (in per cent.).

Food.	Rice.	Casein.	Salts.	Yeast.	Codliver oil.	Addenda.
Mu 1	74	5	3	3 (autoclaved)	15	Aneurin
Mu 2	74	5	3	3	15	Lactoflavin
Mu 5	73	5	3	3	1	14% Peanut oil
Mu 6	74	5	3	3 (whole dried)	1	14% Peanut oil
Mu 7	74	5	3	3	15	Aneurin
Mu 8	74	5	3	3	15	Frankonite filtrate
Mu 9	74	5	3	3	15	Nicotinic acid (2 g.)
Mu 10	62	5	3	15	15	
Mu 12	74	5	3	3	15	Lactoflavin
Mu 13	81	5	3	3	8	
Mu 14	81	5	3	3	8	Aneurin
Mu 15	69	5	3	15	8	
Mu 16	74	5	3	3 (autoclaved)	15	Aneurin and lactoflavin

The results of the feeding experiments are shown in the following tables.

TABLE II.

Rat No.	Weight on		Max. increase.	Food.	Rat No.	Weight on		Max. increase.	Food.
	25-43-8.	9-5-38.				25-4-38.	9-5-38.		
8995	58 g.	40 g.	-18 g.	Mu 1	9001	58 g.	40 g.	-18 g.	Mu 2
8996	57	40	-17	1	9002	59	40	-19	2
8997	59	42	-17	1	9003	62	96	34	5
8998	57	39	-18	1	9015	50	83	33	5
8999	60	46	-14	2	9016	47	78	31	5
9000	54	38	-16	2	9017	51	93	42	5

TABLE III.

Rat No.	Weight on		Max. increase.	Food.	Rat No.	Weight on		Max. increase.	Food.
	1-5-38.	19 7-38.				19-5-38.	1-7-38.		
8995	54 g.	67 g	27 g.	Mu 7	9001	58 g.	46 g.	18 g.	Mu 12
8996	57	79	39	7	9002	63	45	23	12
8997	64	87	45	7	9003	124	171	75	6
8999	54	76	37	7	9015	105	183	100	6
8998	71	49	25	12	9016	98	163	85	6
9000	57	46	19	12	9017	116	197	104	6

TABLE IV.

Rat No.	Weight on		Max. increase.	Food.	Rat No.	Weight on		Max. increase.	Food.
	31-5-38.	1-7-38.				31-5-38.	1-7-38.		
9291	32 g.	62 g.	30 g.	Mu 7	9297	35 g.	77 g.	42 g.	Mu 8
9292	41	74	33	7	9298	28	58	30	8
9293	42	71	29	7	9299	29	65	36	8
9294	45	58	13	7	9300	26	53	27	8
9295	42	70	28	7	9301	29	51	22	8
9296	39	58	19	7	9302	30	57	27	8

TABLE V.

Rat No.	Weight on		Max. increase.	Food.	Rat No.	Weight on		Max. increase.	Food.
	9-5-38.	1-7-38.				9-5-38.	1-7-38.		
9042	64 g.	116 g.	52 g.	Mu 8	9048	46 g.	38 g.	-8 g.	Mu 9
9043	41	95	54	8	9049	46	40	-8	9
9044	60	117	57	8	9050	55	121	66	10
9045	57	110	53	8	9051	53	108	55	10
9046	46	38	-10	9	9052	54	102	48	10
9047	44	38	-9	9	9053	46	104	58	10.

TABLE VI.

Rat No.	Weight on		Max. increase.	Food.	Rat No.	Weight on		Max. increase.	Food.
	4-5-38.	1-7-38.				4-5-38.	1-7-38.		
9054	40 g.	112 g.	72 g.	Mu 13	9060	40 g.	107 g.	67 g.	Mu 14
9055	42	107	65	13	9061	41	116	75	14
9056	45	147	102	13	9062	42	221	179	15
9057	33	113	80	13	9063	42	168	127	15
9058	41	113	72	14	9064	46	183	137	15
9059	45	118	73	14	9065	33	116	83	15

TABLE VII.

Rat No.	Weight on		Max. increase.	Food.	Rat No.	Weight on		Max. increase.	Food.
	23-6-38.	18-7-38.				1-7-38.	18-7-38.		
9407	42 g.	83 g.	41 g.	Mu 12	9433	51 g.	69 g.	44 g.	Mu 12
9408	43	104	61	12	9434	48	72	24	12
9409	46	102	56	12	9435	48	69	21	12
9410	42	86	44	12	9436	46	69	23	12
9411	44	92	38	12	9437	46	62	16	12
9412	42	84	42	12	9438	50	71	21	12

TABLE VIII.

Rat No	Weight on 13-6-38.	Weight on 1-7-38.	Max. increase.	Food.
9297	56 g.	77 g.	21 g.	Mu 8
9298	46	58	12	8
9299	46	65	19	8
9300	41	53	12	8
9301	39	51	12	8
9302	46	57	11	8

TABLE IX.

Rat No.	Weight on 9-6-38.	Weight on 18-7-38	Max. increase.	Food.
9314	57 g.	96 g.	39 g.	Mu 16
9315	48	84	36	16
9316	50	103	53	16
9317	52	82	30	16

DISCUSSION.

In Table II we find that though the vitamins aneurin and lactoflavin were administered in pure forms, they could not neutralise the effects of large amounts of codliver oil when the 3% yeast added was autoclaved. We cannot ascribe the result to the autoclaved yeast alone, since the animals having peanut oil instead of codliver oil had been growing apparently normally though the other factors of the B complex were missing here as with the former groups of animals. In Table III is found that by replacing the 3% autoclaved yeast by dried whole yeast, the animals gained their former weights or more within ten days. After this date the aneurin receiving animals as well as the controls went on gaining weights but all the lactoflavin receiving animals lost weights. In the latter case it is possible that there was some error in the preparation of the food specially there might have been a delay in preparing it fresh within the required time, when the atmosphere being more warm the codliver oil would have turned more toxic. Table IV shows that with the frankonite filtrate of aqueous yeast extract, growth in the animals was appreciably more than with the aneurin administration, specially when we take into consideration the fact that the starting weights in the former case were much below others in our experiments. As a matter of fact in other cases we were not successful with our experiments when so small animals were taken. From Tables V and VI it comes out that extra 12% whole dried yeast is

more effective than frankonite filtrate of yeast extract in neutralising the toxicity of codliver oil and promoting growth. This particular point has all along been noted by De Vries and Puister (*loc. cit.*). Nicotinic acid had all along been found to be ineffective and possibly it is a little toxic as well. Tables VII and VIII show lactoflavin to be more effective than the frankonite filtrate of yeast extract. In Table IX the animals were found to gain weights though autoclaved yeast was used. The difference in this table from Table II is that in Table IX the animals had always a second factor of the B complex in addition to that in Table I, which points to the fact that the different factors of the vitamin B complex together act better.

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